

**A GENERALIZATION OF THE LANDEN CONNECTION
FORMULA AND GENERALIZED POLY-BERNOULLI NUMBERS**

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Abstract

We introduce a generalization of multiple polylogarithms and give their Landen-type connection formulas. Also, we define generalized poly-Bernoulli numbers by using these polylogarithms and prove some relations.

1. Introduction

For an index $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r) \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$, we set $d(\mathbf{k}) := r$ and $|\mathbf{k}| = k := k_1 + \dots + k_r$. They are called the *depth* and the *weight* of \mathbf{k} , respectively. For any index $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r)$, define *multiple polylogarithms* $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(z)$ as

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(z) := \sum_{0 < m_1 < \dots < m_r} \frac{z^{m_r}}{m_1^{k_1} \dots m_r^{k_r}} \in \mathbb{Q}[[z]]$$

(for more general settings, see, e.g., [3] and [16]). When $\mathbf{k} = (k)$ ($k > 0$), the function $\text{Li}_k(z)$ is the classical polylogarithm.

For indices \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{k}' , the notation $\mathbf{k}' \preceq \mathbf{k}$ means that \mathbf{k}' is obtained from \mathbf{k} by combining some consecutive entries, e.g., $(3, 5) \preceq (1, 2, 1, 3, 1)$. Okuda and Ueno [14] proved the following beautiful relation called the Landen connection formula:

Theorem 1 ([14, Prop. 9]). *For any index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$, we have that*

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}\left(\frac{z}{z-1}\right) = (-1)^{d(\mathbf{k})} \sum_{\mathbf{k}' \preceq \mathbf{k}} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}'}(z). \quad (1)$$

Let $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(z)$ be the non-strict multiple polylogarithm defined by

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(z) := \sum_{0 < m_1 \leq \dots \leq m_r} \frac{z^{m_r}}{m_1^{k_1} \dots m_r^{k_r}}.$$

We note that $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(z) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}' \preceq \mathbf{k}} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}'}(z)$. If an index $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r)$ satisfies $k_r \geq 2$, then the values $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(1)$ and $\overline{\text{Li}}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(1)$ converge. These limit values, denoted by $\zeta(\mathbf{k})$ and $\zeta^*(\mathbf{k})$, are called *multiple zeta values* and *multiple zeta star values*, respectively.

For an index $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r)$ with $k_r \geq 2$, Yamamoto [15] introduced the following interpolated multiple zeta values:

$$\zeta^t(\mathbf{k}) := \sum_{\mathbf{k}' \preceq \mathbf{k}} t^{d(\mathbf{k})-d(\mathbf{k}')} \zeta(\mathbf{k}') \in \mathbb{R}[t].$$

This polynomial interpolates multiple zeta values and multiple zeta star values because $\zeta^0(\mathbf{k}) = \zeta(\mathbf{k})$ and $\zeta^1(\mathbf{k}) = \zeta^*(\mathbf{k})$. Yamamoto studied the function $\zeta^t(\mathbf{k})$ in connection with the so-called “two-one formula” [13], and proved a sum formula and a cyclic sum formula for $\zeta^t(\mathbf{k})$.

There are some studies on a polylogarithm version of the interpolated multiple zeta values. Li and Qin [10] introduced interpolated multiple polylogarithms as

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(t, z) := \sum_{\mathbf{k}' \preceq \mathbf{k}} t^{\text{dep}(\mathbf{k})-\text{dep}(\mathbf{k}')} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}'}(z) \tag{2}$$

and gave a formula relating to the so-called “Ohno-Zagier relation” [12]. When $k_r \geq 2$, it clearly follows that $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(t, 1) = \zeta^t(\mathbf{k})$. Ohno and Wayama [11] investigated the interpolated Arakawa-Kaneko zeta functions and considered another type of interpolated multiple polylogarithm as follows:

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^t(z) := \sum_{\mathbf{k} \preceq \mathbf{k}'} t^{\text{dep}(\mathbf{k}')-\text{dep}(\mathbf{k})} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}'}(z). \tag{3}$$

This function interpolates $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^0(z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(z)$ and $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^1(z) = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \preceq \mathbf{k}'} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}'}(z)$. The latter value $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^1(z)$ appears in the Landen connection formula (1).

For an index $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r) \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$, two kinds of poly-Bernoulli numbers $C_n^{(\mathbf{k})}$ and $B_n^{(\mathbf{k})}$ ($n \geq 0$) are defined as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(1 - e^{-t})}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n^{(\mathbf{k})} \frac{t^n}{n!} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(1 - e^{-t})}{1 - e^{-t}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(\mathbf{k})} \frac{t^n}{n!}$$

(see, e.g., [9]). We remark that, in general, these numbers can be defined even if k_i 's are non-positive. When $r = 1$, the numbers $C_n^{(k)}$ and $B_n^{(k)}$ are introduced by Arakawa-Kaneko [1] and Kaneko [6]. Since $\text{Li}_1(z) = -\log(1-z)$, we have $C_n^{(1)} = B_n$ and $B_n^{(1)} = (-1)^n B_n$ for $n \geq 0$. Here B_n ($n \geq 0$) are ordinary Bernoulli numbers defined by

$$\frac{t}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_n}{n!} t^n.$$

In the present paper, we introduce generalized multiple polylogarithms including both Equations (2) and (3) and give a generalization of the Landen connection

formula (1). Moreover, we define the corresponding poly-Bernoulli numbers, which are generalizations of the ordinary poly-Bernoulli numbers $C_n^{(\mathbf{k})}$ and $B_n^{(\mathbf{k})}$, and prove some identities.

2. Generalized Multiple Polylogarithms

For a matrix $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in GL_2(\mathbb{R})$, let us consider $z = \frac{ae^t + b}{ce^t + d}$ which is a linear fractional transformation of e^t . We remark that $z = \frac{ae^t + b}{ce^t + d}$ can be written *formally* as

$$t = \log \frac{-b + dz}{a - cz} = \int_{\frac{a+b}{c+d}}^z \left(\frac{c}{a - cu} - \frac{d}{b - du} \right) du. \tag{4}$$

In particular, when $a = 1$ and $b = -1$, we have

$$t = \log \frac{1 + dz}{1 - cz} = \int_0^z \left(\frac{c}{1 - cu} + \frac{d}{1 + du} \right) du. \tag{5}$$

For an integer $s \geq 1$, set $g_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ c_0 & d_0 \end{pmatrix} \in GL_2(\mathbb{R})$ and $g_i = \begin{pmatrix} a_i & b_i \\ c_i & d_i \end{pmatrix} \in GL_2(\mathbb{R})$ ($1 \leq i \leq s$). The symbol \mathbf{g} stands for a sequence $\mathbf{g} = (g_0, g_1, \dots, g_s)$. Let $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_s)$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_s) \in \mathbb{R}^s$.

For an index $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r) \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$, we use the arrow notation $\mathbf{k}_\uparrow := (k_1, \dots, k_r + 1)$ and $\mathbf{k}_\rightarrow := (k_1, \dots, k_r, 1)$. Then we define generalized multiple polylogarithms $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) \in \mathbb{R}[[z]]$ inductively as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}_\uparrow}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) &= \int_0^z \sum_{i=1}^s \beta_i \left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i u} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i u} \right) \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); u) du, \\ \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}_\rightarrow}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) &= \int_0^z \sum_{i=1}^s \gamma_i \left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i u} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i u} \right) \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); u) du \end{aligned}$$

with an initial condition

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Li}_{(1)}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) &= \int_0^z \left(\frac{c_0}{1 - c_0 u} + \frac{d_0}{1 + d_0 u} \right) du \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{c_0^n - (-d_0)^n}{n} z^n. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here we give some examples of $g = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ and $G_g(t) := \frac{c}{a-ct} - \frac{d}{b-dt}$ in Table 1.

g	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -w \end{pmatrix} (w \neq 1)$
$G_g(t)$	$\frac{1}{t}$	$\frac{1}{1-t}$	$\frac{2}{1-t^2}$	$\frac{1}{1-t} - \frac{w}{1-wt}$

Table 1: Examples of $G_g(t)$

If $\mathbf{g} = (g_0, g_1, g_2)$ with $g_0 = g_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ and $g_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, and $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (1, 0)$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = (0, 1)$, then the function $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z)$ is expressed by the well-known iterated integral representation of the multiple polylogarithm $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(z)$. By definition, the function $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z)$ has no constant term, i.e., $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) \in z\mathbb{R}[[z]]$ for any index \mathbf{k} . Also it follows that $\text{Li}_{(1)}\left(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0}\right) = t$ because of Equation (4).

For an index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^s$, Hoffman’s dual index \mathbf{k}^\vee of \mathbf{k} is defined inductively by the identities $(\mathbf{k}_\uparrow)^\vee = (\mathbf{k}^\vee)_\rightarrow$ and $(\mathbf{k}_\rightarrow)^\vee = (\mathbf{k}^\vee)_\uparrow$ with $(1)^\vee = (1)$. This index \mathbf{k}^\vee appears in Hoffman’s duality formula for finite multiple zeta values (see [4]). Interchanging $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ corresponds to taking Hoffman’s dual index \mathbf{k}^\vee , i.e., the following identity holds:

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}^\vee}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\beta}); z).$$

The following is a kind of sum formula for $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z)$.

Proposition 1. For an integer $k \geq 1$ and an indeterminate μ , we have

$$\sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mu\boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\delta}); z). \tag{7}$$

Here $\boldsymbol{\delta} \in \mathbb{R}^s$ is an arbitrary vector and $\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mu\boldsymbol{\gamma} := (\beta_i + \mu\gamma_i)_{1 \leq i \leq s}$.

Proof. We prove Identity (7) by induction on k . When $k = 1$, Identity (7) is trivial because $\text{Li}_{(1)}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z)$ defined by Identity (6) does not depend on $(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma})$.

We assume that Identity (7) holds for some $k \geq 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dz} \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k+1} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) \\ &= \frac{d}{dz} \left(\sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}_\uparrow}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) + \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}_\rightarrow}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^s \beta_i \left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i z} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i z} \right) \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sum_{i=1}^s \mu \gamma_i \left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i z} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i z} \right) \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) \\
 & = \sum_{i=1}^s (\beta_i + \mu \gamma_i) \left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i z} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i z} \right) \text{Li}_k(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mu \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\delta}); z).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by inductive assumption, we have

$$\frac{d}{dz} \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k+1} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z) = \frac{d}{dz} \text{Li}_{k+1}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mu \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\delta}); z).$$

Because every multiple polylogarithm has no constant term, Identity (7) also holds for $k + 1$. □

For $\mathbf{g} = (g_0, g_1, \dots, g_s)$, we define

$$\tilde{g}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{a}_i & \tilde{b}_i \\ \tilde{c}_i & \tilde{d}_i \end{pmatrix} := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ c_0 - d_0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} g_i = \begin{pmatrix} a_i & b_i \\ (c_0 - d_0)a_i - c_i & (c_0 - d_0)b_i - d_i \end{pmatrix}$$

for $0 \leq i \leq s$ and set $\tilde{\mathbf{g}} = (\tilde{g}_0, \tilde{g}_1, \dots, \tilde{g}_s)$. We remark that each \tilde{g}_i ($1 \leq i \leq s$) depends on g_0 and

$$\tilde{g}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ c_0 - d_0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ c_0 & d_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -d_0 & -c_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Also we can see that this operation is an involution, i.e., $(\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}}) = \mathbf{g}$. Then we obtain the following theorem which is a generalization of the Landen connection formula (1).

Theorem 2. For any index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$, we have

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); \frac{z}{(c_0 - d_0)z - 1} \right) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\tilde{\mathbf{g}}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z). \tag{8}$$

Proof. We will prove the following: if $u = \frac{v}{(c_0 - d_0)v - 1}$, then

$$\left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i u} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i u} \right) du = \left(\frac{\tilde{c}_i}{\tilde{a}_i - \tilde{c}_i v} - \frac{\tilde{d}_i}{\tilde{b}_i - \tilde{d}_i v} \right) dv \quad (1 \leq i \leq s).$$

Then, by considering the transformation of variables, we obtain Equation (8).

When $u = \frac{v}{(c_0 - d_0)v - 1}$, we have $du = \frac{-1}{((c_0 - d_0)v - 1)^2} dv$ and

$$\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i u} du = \frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i \frac{v}{(c_0 - d_0)v - 1}} \cdot \frac{-1}{((c_0 - d_0)v - 1)^2} dv$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{c_i}{(a_i(c_0 - d_0) - c_i)v - a_i} \cdot \frac{-1}{(c_0 - d_0)v - 1} dv \\
 &= \left(\frac{a_i(c_0 - d_0) - c_i}{a_i - (a_i(c_0 - d_0) - c_i)v} - \frac{c_0 - d_0}{1 - (c_0 - d_0)v} \right) dv.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left(\frac{c_i}{a_i - c_i u} - \frac{d_i}{b_i - d_i u} \right) du &= \left(\frac{a_i(c_0 - d_0) - c_i}{a_i - (a_i(c_0 - d_0) - c_i)v} - \frac{b_i(c_0 - d_0) - d_i}{b_i - (b_i(c_0 - d_0) - d_i)v} \right) dv \\
 &= \left(\frac{\tilde{c}_i}{\tilde{a}_i - \tilde{c}_i v} - \frac{\tilde{d}_i}{\tilde{b}_i - \tilde{d}_i v} \right) dv.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

3. Examples

3.1. The Classical Case

Throughout this subsection we assume that $s = 2$ and

$$\mathbf{g} = (g_0, g_1, g_2) \text{ with } g_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, g_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } g_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

The function $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, ((\beta_1, \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)); z)$ is a generalization of both $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(t, z)$ and $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^t(z)$ defined by Equations (2) and (3). In fact, we have

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, ((1, 0), (t, 1)); z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(t, z) \text{ and } \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, ((1, t), (0, 1)); z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^t(z).$$

We give some examples of the correspondence of g and $G_g(t)$ in Table 2.

$g_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$g_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$g_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
$G_{g_0}(t) = \frac{1}{1-t}$	$G_{g_1}(t) = \frac{1}{t}$	$G_{g_2}(t) = \frac{1}{1-t}$
$\tilde{g}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\tilde{g}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\tilde{g}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$
$G_{\tilde{g}_0}(t) = -\frac{1}{1-t}$	$G_{\tilde{g}_1}(t) = \frac{1}{1-t} + \frac{1}{t}$	$G_{\tilde{g}_2}(t) = -\frac{1}{1-t}$

Table 2: Examples of $G_{g_i}(t)$ and $G_{\tilde{g}_i}(t)$

Under the assumption (9), Theorem 2 can be written in the following form.

Theorem 3. Assume \mathbf{g} satisfies the condition (9). Then

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, ((\beta_1, \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)); \frac{z}{z-1} \right) = -\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, ((\beta_1, \beta_1 - \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_1 - \gamma_2)); z \right). \tag{10}$$

Proof. By Theorem 2, we have

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, ((\beta_1, \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)); \frac{z}{z-1} \right) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} (\tilde{\mathbf{g}}, ((\beta_1, \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)); z). \tag{11}$$

The differential form $\beta_1 \frac{1}{t} dt + \beta_2 \frac{1}{1-t} dt$ is transformed as

$$\left(\beta_1 \left(\frac{1}{t} + \frac{1}{1-t} \right) + \beta_2 \left(-\frac{1}{1-t} \right) \right) dt = \left(\beta_1 \frac{1}{t} + (\beta_1 - \beta_2) \frac{1}{1-t} \right) dt$$

under the transformation $t \mapsto \frac{t}{t-1}$. Hence we have

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} (\tilde{\mathbf{g}}, ((\beta_1, \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)); z) = -\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} (\mathbf{g}, ((\beta_1, \beta_1 - \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_1 - \gamma_2)); z)$$

and this completes the proof. □

Example 1. By applying $(\beta_1, \beta_2) = (1, t)$ and $(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) = (0, 1)$ in Equation (10), we obtain that

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^t \left(\frac{z}{z-1} \right) = (-1)^{d(\mathbf{k})} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^{1-t}(z),$$

where $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^t(z)$ is the function defined by Equation (3). When $t = 0$, this equation gives the original Landen connection formula (1).

Example 2. For $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, set $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\beta)}(z) := \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, ((1, \beta), (1, 1 - \beta)); z)$. By Theorem 3, we can get

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\beta)} \left(\frac{z}{z-1} \right) = -\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{k}^\vee}^{(\beta)}(z). \tag{12}$$

In particular, when $\beta = 0$, this equation gives

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^* \left(\frac{z}{z-1} \right) = -\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}^\vee}^*(z).$$

3.2. A Case with One Parameter

Throughout this subsection we assume that $s = 2$ and

$$\mathbf{g} = (g_0, g_1, g_2) \text{ with } g_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -w \end{pmatrix}, g_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } g_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -w \end{pmatrix},$$

$g_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -w \end{pmatrix}$	$g_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$g_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -w \end{pmatrix}$
$G_{g_0}(t) = \frac{1}{1-t} - \frac{w}{1-wt}$	$G_{g_1}(t) = \frac{1}{t}$	$G_{g_2}(t) = \frac{1}{1-t} - \frac{w}{1-wt}$
$\tilde{g}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ w & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\tilde{g}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1+w & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\tilde{g}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ w & -1 \end{pmatrix}$
$G_{\tilde{g}_0}(t) = -\frac{1}{1-t} + \frac{w}{1-wt}$	$G_{\tilde{g}_1}(t) = \frac{1+w}{1-(1+w)t} + \frac{1}{t}$	$G_{\tilde{g}_2}(t) = -\frac{1}{1-t} + \frac{w}{1-wt}$

Table 3: Examples of $G_{g_i}(t)$ and $G_{\tilde{g}_i}(t)$ with a parameter w

where w is a real parameter with $-1 \leq w < 1$. The case $w = 0$ is the one treated in the previous section.

We also give a correspondence between g and $G_g(t)$ in Table 3.

If $\beta = (1, 0)$ and $\gamma = (0, 1)$, then the function $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(g, (\beta, \gamma); z)$ coincides with the function $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(w)}(z)$ defined by the author [5] (in [5] the parameter c is used instead of w and the function is denoted by $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^c(z)$). The value $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(w)}(1)$ is the *multiple T-value with one parameter* defined by Chapoton [2].

When $w = 0$, we have $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(z)$ and when $w = -1$, we have $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(-1)}(z) = 2^{d(\mathbf{k})} \text{Ath}(\mathbf{k}, z)$. Here $\text{Ath}(\mathbf{k}, z)$ is a kind of multiple polylogarithm of level two defined by

$$\text{Ath}(\mathbf{k}, z) := \sum_{\substack{m_i \equiv 1(2) \\ m_i > 0}} \frac{z^{m_1 + \dots + m_r}}{m_1^{k_1} (m_1 + m_2)^{k_2} \dots (m_1 + \dots + m_r)^{k_r}}$$

(see [7, Eq. (5.1)]). By Theorem 2, we get the following Landen-type connection formula:

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(w)}\left(\frac{z}{(w+1)z-1}\right) = (-1)^{d(\mathbf{k})} \tilde{\text{Li}}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(w)}(z).$$

Here

$$\tilde{\text{Li}}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(w)}(z) = \sum_{m_1 \geq 1, m_2 \geq 0, \dots, m_k \geq 0} \frac{R(1) \dots R(k)}{m_1(m_1 + m_2) \dots (m_1 + \dots + m_k)} z^{m_1 + \dots + m_k},$$

where

$$R(i) := \begin{cases} 1 - w^{m_i} & (i \in \{1, k_1 + 1, \dots, k_1 + \dots + k_{r-1} + 1\}), \\ (1 + w)^{m_i} & (\text{otherwise}). \end{cases}$$

4. Generalized Poly-Bernoulli Numbers

Imatomi [8] introduced two kinds of multi-poly-Bernoulli-star numbers $C_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})}$ and $B_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})}$ ($n \geq 0$) by the following generating series:

$$\frac{\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(1 - e^{-t})}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})} \frac{t^n}{n!}, \tag{13}$$

$$\frac{\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(1 - e^{-t})}{1 - e^{-t}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})} \frac{t^n}{n!}. \tag{14}$$

The following is a duality formula for multi-poly-Bernoulli-star numbers.

Theorem 4 ([8, Theorem 3.2]). *For an index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$ and an integer $n \geq 0$, we have that*

$$C_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})} = (-1)^n B_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k}^\vee)}.$$

It can be easily checked that the left-hand sides of Equations (13) and (14) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(1 - e^{-t})}{e^t - 1} &= \frac{d}{dt} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}\uparrow}^*(1 - e^{-t}), \\ \frac{\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(1 - e^{-t})}{1 - e^{-t}} &= \frac{d}{dt} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}\rightarrow}^*(1 - e^{-t}). \end{aligned}$$

As an analogy, we define two types of Bernoulli numbers $C_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))}$ and $B_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}\uparrow} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0} \right) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))} \frac{t^n}{n!}, \\ \frac{d}{dt} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}\rightarrow} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0} \right) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))} \frac{t^n}{n!}. \end{aligned}$$

These numbers are generalizations of multi-poly-Bernoulli-star numbers defined by Equations (13) and (14). In fact, if \mathbf{g} satisfies the condition (9) and $\beta = (1, 1)$ and $\gamma = (0, 1)$, then $\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma); z) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(z)$ and we have $C_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))} = C_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})}$ and $B_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))} = B_{n,\star}^{(\mathbf{k})}$. By definition, it is clear that $B_n^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{g},(\beta,\gamma))} = C_n^{(\mathbf{k}^\vee, \mathbf{g}, (\gamma, \beta))}$ and these values are essentially the same objects.

By straightforward calculation, an explicit expression of the generating function

of $C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma))}$ can be given as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}\uparrow} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0} \right) &= \sum_{i=1}^s \beta_i \left(\frac{a_i d_0 + c_i}{(a_i c_0 - c_i) e^t + a_i d_0 + c_i} - \frac{b_i d_0 + d_i}{(b_i c_0 - d_i) e^t + b_i d_0 + d_i} \right) \\ &\times \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

The generating function of $B_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma))}$ is obtained by replacing β_i with γ_i in the right-hand side of the above equation.

By the sum formula (Proposition 1), we get the following proposition.

Proposition 2. *For an integer $k \geq 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma))} = B_n^{(k, \mathbf{g}, (\beta + \mu\gamma, \beta))} = C_n^{\{\{1\}^k, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \beta + \mu\gamma)\}}, \tag{16}$$

$$\sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} B_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma))} = B_n^{(k, \mathbf{g}, (\beta + \mu\gamma, \gamma))} = C_n^{\{\{1\}^k, \mathbf{g}, (\gamma, \beta + \mu\gamma)\}}. \tag{17}$$

Here $\{1\}^k$ stands for the index $\overbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}^k$ for $k \geq 1$.

Proof. We prove only Identity (16), and Identity (17) can be proved similarly. By Proposition 1, we have

$$\sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0} \right) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\mathbf{g}, (\beta + \mu\gamma, \beta); \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0} \right). \tag{18}$$

By multiplying

$$\sum_{i=1}^s \beta_i \left(\frac{a_i d_0 + c_i}{(a_i c_0 - c_i) e^t + a_i d_0 + c_i} - \frac{b_i d_0 + d_i}{(b_i c_0 - d_i) e^t + b_i d_0 + d_i} \right)$$

both sides of Equation (18) and by considering the generating function (15) of $C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma))}$, we have

$$\sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=k} \mu^{d(\mathbf{k})-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\beta, \gamma))} \frac{t^n}{n!} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k, \mathbf{g}, (\beta + \mu\gamma, \beta))} \frac{t^n}{n!}. \tag{19}$$

By comparing the coefficients, we obtain the first equation of (16). The second equation is obtained immediately because of $(k)^\vee = \{1\}^k$. □

By using Theorem 2, we can get the following theorem.

Theorem 5. For any index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}^r$, we have

$$C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}))} = (-1)^{n-1} C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \tilde{\mathbf{g}}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}))} \quad (n \geq 0).$$

Proof. Set $u(z) := \frac{z}{(c_0 - d_0)z - 1}$ and $z(t) := \frac{e^t - 1}{c_0 e^t + d_0}$. Then we can easily show that $u(z(t)) = z(-t)$. By this identity and Theorem 2, we have

$$\text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}_\uparrow}(\mathbf{g}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z(t)) = \text{Li}_{\mathbf{k}_\uparrow}(\tilde{\mathbf{g}}, (\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}); z(-t)).$$

By differentiating both sides in t and comparing the coefficients, the desired identity is obtained. \square

In the last of the paper, we give a formula which generalizes Theorem 4. Assume that \mathbf{g} satisfies the condition (9). Substituting $z = 1 - e^t$ in Identity (12), we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\beta)}(1 - e^{-t}) = -\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{k}^\vee}^{(\beta)}(1 - e^t).$$

By the relation $(\mathbf{k}_\uparrow)^\vee = (\mathbf{k}^\vee)_\rightarrow$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{k}_\uparrow}^{(\beta)}(1 - e^{-t}) = -\mathcal{L}_{(\mathbf{k}^\vee)_\rightarrow}^{(\beta)}(1 - e^t).$$

By differentiating both sides of this equation with respect to t and by comparing the coefficients, we obtain that

$$C_n^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{g}, ((1, \beta), (1, 1 - \beta)))} = (-1)^n B_n^{(\mathbf{k}^\vee, \mathbf{g}, ((1, \beta), (1, 1 - \beta)))} \quad (n \geq 0).$$

This formula gives Theorem 4 when $\beta = 0$.

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